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MARKETING MIX OF FOOD DELIVERY SERVICE BY ZOMATO IN BANGALORE AND THE IMPACT OF CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT

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Abstract

This study aims to analyse the marketing mix strategies implemented by Zomato, a prominent food delivery service in Bangalore, and explore the impact on customer engagement on its business performance. The study focuses on understanding the key elements of Zomato's marketing mix, including product, price, place, and promotion, and their effectiveness in attracting and retaining customers. Furthermore, the study examines the relationship between customer engagement and various performance indicators, such as customer satisfaction, loyalty, and word-of-mouth referrals. The research employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative data from surveys conducted among Zomato customers in Bangalore with qualitative insights gathered through online available interviews of Zomato's marketing and customer service teams. The survey responses were collected from a sample of 100 Zomato customers, ensuring a diverse representation of demographic characteristics and usage patterns. The findings of this study contribute to the existing literature on food delivery services and marketing mix strategies by providing empirical evidence on the effectiveness of Zomato's marketing efforts in the Bangalore market. The results shed light on the significance of customer engagement as a key driver of business success in the food delivery industry, highlighting the importance of building strong relationships with customers through personalized experiences, timely communication, and responsiveness to feedback.

Keywords: Zomato, food delivery service, marketing mix, customer engagement, Bangalore, customer satisfaction, loyalty, word-of-mouth referrals, surveys, qualitative research.

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INTRODUCTION

In today's fast-paced world, the demand for convenient and efficient food delivery services has witnessed an unprecedented surge. One such prominent player in the food delivery industry is Zomato, a leading online platform that connects customers with a wide range of restaurants in Bangalore, India. Zomato has become synonymous with convenience, offering a diverse array of culinary options delivered right to the customers' doorstep.

The success of Zomato, like any other food delivery service, relies heavily on its marketing mix. The marketing mix refers to a set of strategic elements that a company utilizes to promote its products or services to the target market. These elements, including product, price, place, and promotion, work collectively to create a compelling value proposition and drive customer engagement.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the marketing mix of Zomato in Bangalore and examine the impact of customer engagement on its overall success. By

delving into each element of the marketing mix, such as the range of food offerings, competitive pricing, efficient delivery logistics, and effective promotional campaigns, this study aims to shed light on the strategies employed by Zomato to attract and retain customers in the highly competitive food delivery market.

This study on the marketing mix of Zomato in Bangalore and the impact of customer engagement aims to provide valuable insights for marketers, businesses, and researchers in understanding the dynamics of the rapidly evolving food delivery industry and the strategies employed by successful players like Zomato. Include Product, Price, Place & Promotion

The marketing mix works collectively to create a compelling value proposition for Zomato's customers, making it a convenient and attractive option for ordering food.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of this study are as follows:

- To study the marketing mix elements (product, price, place, promotion) employed by Zomato in the food delivery market in Bangalore.
- To analyze the impact of the marketing mix on customer engagement with Zomato.
- To ascertain the level of customer satisfaction and loyalty towards Zomato's services.
- To understand the preferences and needs of customers regarding the marketing mix elements.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. Limited sample size: The study will be conducted with a sample size of 100 Zomato customers in Bangalore, which may not fully represent the diverse range of customers and their preferences.
2. Geographical scope: The study focuses solely on Zomato's operations in Bangalore, limiting the generalizability of findings to other regions.
3. Time constraints: Conducting a comprehensive study within a limited timeframe may restrict the depth and breadth of data collection and analysis.

4. Reliance on self-reported data: The study relies on customers' self-reported opinions and perceptions, which may be subject to response biases or inaccuracies.
5. External factors: The study may not account for external factors, such as macroeconomic conditions or changes in the competitive landscape, which could influence customer engagement.
6. Availability and reliability of secondary data: The quality and availability of secondary data may vary, which could affect the completeness and accuracy of the analysis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The competitive dynamics are influenced by these forces, as demonstrated by Saha, S. (2023), in the case of the Air India acquisition in the aviation industry.

The significance of threshold values in sales performance factors, such as customer acquisition cost and sales conversion rates, extends beyond mere metrics; they are pivotal determinants of a company's competitive advantage and its position within the industry (Saha, 2023).

Similarly, organizations with high levels of employee dissatisfaction or inefficient processes may struggle to innovate or compete effectively, impacting the intensity of rivalry among competitors (Saha, S., 2023)

Vendor capability, particularly the ability to deliver high-quality products or services, can significantly impact the power dynamics within the relationship, affecting pricing and trade terms (Saha, S., & Joshi, K., 2024).

Saha & Kar (2021) propose that the computation of sales performance scores and effective cross-functional collaboration can deter new entrants and retain bargaining power with customers in the IT/ITES industry.

The performance of salespeople, influenced by factors such as personality traits, product knowledge, competitive intelligence, and the utilization of sales force automation, can significantly affect the bargaining power of buyers and suppliers through their impact on purchasing decisions and negotiation outcomes (Saha & Kar, 2021).

Cross-functional sales performance variables, such as customer satisfaction and market responsiveness, play a crucial role in mitigating the threat of

substitutes in the IT/ITES sector (Saha & Kumari, 2019).

A vendor's established capability and experience in Business-to-Business (B2B) transactions can strengthen a company's competitive position by reducing the bargaining power of buyers, as clients are more likely to award contracts to trusted vendors with proven track records (Saha, S., & Joshi, K., 2021).

In a review of "The 22 Immutable Laws of Marketing," Saha, S., et al. emphasize that in competitive markets, reducing competitive rivalry—a core component of Porter's Five Forces—requires companies to focus on differentiation, unique market positioning, niche marketing, distinct product attributes, and consistent brand messaging.

Moreover, advancements in technology and cross-functional factors enabling automated sales processes can lower the bargaining power of suppliers by reducing dependence on traditional sales personnel (Saha, S., 2024).

The acquisition of New Delhi Television Limited (NDTV) by the Adani Group signifies a significant competitive change in the Indian media industry, showcasing how large conglomerates can use corporate takeovers to gain substantial control and potentially diminish competitive rivalry (Saha, S., et al., 2024).

The merger of PVR and Inox, two leading Indian cinema industry giants, illustrates a strategic response to the increased competitive pressure from OTT platforms, aiming to reduce the threat of substitutes and leverage synergies to regain a competitive edge in a post-COVID landscape (Saha, S., 2024).

The merger between HDFC Bank and HDFC Ltd. creates a stronger banking competitor, with more cross-selling opportunities, increased mortgage disbursements, and a larger customer base, potentially raising barriers to entry and lowering buyer bargaining power due to a broader product and service portfolio (Saha, S., 2024).

COMPANY PROFILE

Launched in 2010, Zomato's technology platform connects customers, restaurant partners and delivery partners, serving their multiple needs. Customers use their platform to search and discover restaurants, read and write customer generated reviews and view and upload photos, order food delivery, book a table and make payments while dining-out at restaurants. On the other hand, they also provide restaurant partners with industry-specific marketing tools which enable them to engage and acquire customers to grow their business while also providing a reliable and efficient last mile delivery service. They also operate a one-stop procurement solution, Hyperpure, which supplies high quality ingredients and kitchen products to restaurant partners. In addition to all above they also provide their delivery partners with transparent and flexible earning opportunities.

ZOMATO STOCK PRICE HISTORY

Zomato's Stock: A Recent Surge with Long-Term Potential

Zomato's stock has been on a roller coaster ride in recent times. Let's take a closer look at its performance:

Fig 1: Zomato's stock price

Short-Term:

- **Past Week:** Zomato has seen a slight dip of 0.38%.
- **Past Month:** However, it has managed to climb 3.88% in the last month.
- **Today (May 16, 2024):** Today, the stock is up 1.25%, trading at ₹194.40.

Long-Term:

The impressive part of Zomato's performance is its long-term growth. Over the past year, the stock price has skyrocketed by a staggering 208.33%, more than tripling in value. This indicates strong investor confidence in the company's future potential.

Volatility:

It's important to remember that Zomato's stock is still relatively young and can be volatile. The recent dip over the past week shows this.

Future Outlook:

Analysts are divided on Zomato's future. Some believe the company's strong growth potential in the Indian food delivery market justifies its current valuation. Others are concerned about Zomato's profitability, as the company is still burning cash.

Recent Developments:

The recent board meeting to discuss audited results could be a sign that Zomato is making progress towards profitability. This could be a positive catalyst for the stock price.

Overall:

Zomato's stock has had a strong run in the long term, but there is still some short-term volatility. The company's future success will depend on its ability to

achieve profitability and maintain its growth trajectory.

ZOMATO MARKETING STRATEGIES

Content Marketing: Content plays a crucial role in Zomato's digital marketing strategy. The platform publishes engaging articles, blog posts, and videos on topics ranging from food trends to restaurant reviews. By providing valuable and entertaining content, Zomato establishes itself as a trusted source of information for food enthusiasts, driving traffic to its website and app.

Every modern brand understands the value of marketing in enabling its growth story, and Zomato is definitely one of them. Since its inception, Zomato's

marketing strategy has been stellar. The food delivery app focuses on creating content that is ideal for its audience, which includes people between 18-35 years of age.

Zomato focuses on leveraging the trends in the market and uniquely connecting them to the brand. So, from sitcoms and sporting events to any other trend in the market, Zomato's marketing team has created content that creates a buzz for all the right reasons.

Nowadays, apps use notifications and timely messages to grab attention, but if the message is too pushy, customers are more likely to ignore it or even go a step further to block it. Zomato ensures that even its notifications are interesting and something the customer will look forward to. Its **cheeky humor** was even noticed in below-mentioned screenshot. Not only does it add humor, but it also delivers the message in a way that is subtle yet interesting.

Social Media Marketing: Zomato utilizes popular social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter to engage with users and promote its services. Through creative content, interactive campaigns, and timely responses to customer queries, Zomato fosters a strong social media presence, attracting and retaining a dedicated following.

Relatable social media memes

On social media, Zomato is a name to reckon with, not only for its services, but the incredible content it creates to interact with its large customer base. The brand not only posts memes relating to external topics, but it has the ability to make fun of itself too. Take its Twitter profile for example, which is full of hilarious content, all of which ultimately focuses on the brand's offerings. Zomato understands that food cravings are real. In keeping with that, it publishes content that is amusing, yet focused on reminding the audience to order food from them.

Search Engine Optimization (SEO): Zomato optimizes its website and app for search engines, ensuring high visibility in organic search results. By targeting relevant keywords and providing quality content, Zomato attracts organic traffic from users seeking restaurant recommendations, food delivery services, and culinary insights.

Influencer Marketing: Collaborating with influencers and food bloggers allows Zomato to reach new audiences and amplify its brand message. By partnering with influential personalities in the food and lifestyle niche, Zomato extends its reach, builds credibility, and generates buzz around its platform.

User-generated Content: Zomato encourages users to contribute reviews, ratings, and photos of their dining experiences. By harnessing user-generated content, Zomato enriches its platform with authentic, real-time insights, helping users make informed decisions about where to eat and order food.

OUTCOMES

- **Increased Brand Awareness:** Zomato's strategic digital marketing efforts have contributed to heightened brand visibility and recognition across various online channels.

- **Enhanced User Engagement:** By fostering a vibrant community of food enthusiasts, Zomato

drives user engagement and interaction, leading to increased app usage and customer loyalty.

- **Improved Customer Acquisition:** Through targeted digital marketing campaigns, Zomato attracts new users and expands its customer base, fueling business growth and market expansion.
- **Strengthened Competitive Position:** Zomato's innovative digital marketing strategies enable it to stay ahead of competitors and maintain its position as a market leader in the food delivery industry.

HOW ZOMATO IS DIFFERENT FROM ITS COMPETITORS

Zomato's Competitive Edge: A Deeper Dive: While competitors like Swiggy and Uber Eats offer similar food delivery services, Zomato has carved out a distinct space for itself through a multi-pronged approach:

Expanding Beyond Delivery:

- **Restaurant Discovery:** Zomato started as a restaurant aggregator, offering in-depth information, menus, and user reviews. This established them as a trusted resource for foodies, helping users discover new restaurants and make informed choices before even placing an order.
- **Table Reservations:** Zomato allows users to book tables at restaurants, integrating the entire dining experience within their platform. This caters to users who might prefer to dine out but don't want the hassle of waiting for a table.
- **Delivery Versatility:** In some regions, Zomato goes beyond just food delivery. They might deliver groceries, pharmacy items, or other essentials, creating a one-stop shop for various needs.

Data-Driven Approach:

- **Fighting Fraud:** Zomato employs a dedicated team that uses data analysis to identify and remove fraudulent restaurant listings or

misleading reviews. This ensures a trustworthy user experience and protects both restaurants and customers.

- **Predictive Power:** Zomato leverages AI to analyze historical order data, predicting future demand for specific dishes and cuisines at partnered restaurants. By sharing these insights, they help restaurants optimize their inventory, reduce food waste, and ensure popular items are always available.

User-Centric Experience:

- **AI-powered Assistance:** Zomato's AI chatbots offer a seamless user experience. Unlike some AI tools that require specific prompts, Zomato's chatbots can handle natural language conversations, answering various food-related questions and guiding users through the platform.
- **Focus on Usability:** Positive reviews highlight Zomato's user-friendly interface, making it easy to find restaurants, browse menus, place orders, and track deliveries.
- **Deals and Customer Service:** Zomato is known for offering deals and discounts, making food ordering more affordable. They also prioritize customer service, ensuring a smooth experience in case of any issues.

Content and Marketing Strategy: While this wasn't explicitly mentioned earlier, Zomato's content and marketing strategy also set them apart. They create relatable and engaging content, like the "Humans of Zomato" series, which fosters a connection with users. Additionally, their witty social media presence helps them stand out in a crowded marketplace.

The Competitive Landscape: It's crucial to remember that the food delivery market is highly competitive. Companies like Swiggy and Uber Eats are constantly innovating. However, Zomato's focus on a comprehensive user experience, data-driven insights, and a commitment to fighting fraud positions them as a strong contender in the race for hungry customers.

ZOMATO'S CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY

Zomato Bangalore recognizes the importance of customer engagement and has implemented several initiatives to foster it. These initiatives can include:

Personalized Communication: Zomato Bangalore communicates with customers on a personalized level, addressing them by name and tailoring offers and recommendations based on their

preferences and order history. This approach enhances the customer's sense of being valued and understood.

Loyalty Programs: Zomato Bangalore offers loyalty programs that reward customers for their repeat business. These programs can include points-based systems, exclusive discounts, or special privileges for loyal customers. By rewarding and acknowledging their loyalty, Zomato Bangalore encourages continued engagement and brand loyalty.

Social Media Engagement: Zomato Bangalore actively engages with customers on social media platforms. They respond to customer inquiries, reviews, and comments promptly and positively. This interaction creates a sense of community and builds trust with the customers.

Interactive Marketing Campaigns: Zomato Bangalore conducts interactive marketing campaigns, such as contests, quizzes, and user-generated content initiatives. These campaigns encourage customers to actively participate and engage with the brand, creating a sense of belonging and fostering brand loyalty.

Seamless User Experience: Zomato Bangalore focuses on providing a seamless and convenient user experience through their website and mobile app. They continuously optimize their platforms to make ordering food as easy and efficient as possible. By ensuring a smooth user experience, Zomato Bangalore enhances customer satisfaction and engagement.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

TYPE OF STUDY: This research study will primarily adopt a descriptive research design. It aims to provide a detailed analysis and understanding of the marketing mix elements employed by Zomato and their impact on customer engagement in the Bangalore food delivery market.

SOURCES OF DATA

Primary Data: The primary data for this study will be collected personally by the researcher using a structured questionnaire administered to Zomato customers in Bangalore. The data will be collected specifically for the purpose of this study, focusing on customers' perceptions of the marketing mix elements and their engagement with Zomato.

Secondary Data: Secondary data will be sourced from published materials, including journals, publications, and relevant online sources. It will

encompass existing data collected by others for different purposes, such as market reports, industry analyses, and customer reviews.

SAMPLING PLAN

Sampling unit: The sampling unit for this study will be Zomato customers in Bangalore who have used the food delivery service at least once in the past six months.

Sample size: The study will aim to collect responses from 100 Zomato customers in Bangalore to ensure a representative sample.

Sampling technique: The sampling technique employed will be a Google Survey using a structured questionnaire. The survey will be distributed to Zomato customers randomly selected from the target population.

TOOLS & TECHNIQUES OF DATA COLLECTION

The data collection process will utilize the following tools and techniques:

- **Survey:** A structured questionnaire will be developed, including Likert scale options, to gather customer opinions and perceptions regarding the marketing mix elements and customer engagement.
- **Observation:** Observations will be made during the data collection process to note any non-verbal cues or behavioral patterns of the respondents.

PLAN OF ANALYSIS:

The collected data will be compiled, classified, and tabulated for analysis. The analysis will involve interpreting and inferring the data to draw meaningful conclusions. The study will utilize percentage analysis to understand the distribution of responses across different variables.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

Based on the analysis of responses collected for above questionnaire, following inference was drawn:

1. **Gender Distribution:** The study consisted of 54% male and 46% female participants, indicating a relatively balanced representation.
2. **Age Distribution:** The majority of participants fell into the age group of 18-25 (28%) and 46 and above (30%), with smaller proportions in the 26-35 (23%) and 36-45 (19%) age groups.

3. **Occupation:** The largest occupational group among the participants was full-time employed individuals (45%), followed by students (22%) and part-time employed individuals (13%).
4. **Monthly Income:** The income distribution showed that participants with incomes between ₹20,000-₹40,000 (28%) and ₹40,000-₹60,000 (24%) were relatively more represented.
5. **Frequency of Using Zomato:** The most common frequency of using Zomato's food delivery service was once a week (39%), followed by 2-3 times a week (27%) and occasionally (22%).
6. **Awareness Source:** Social media (51%) was the most common source through which participants first heard about Zomato's food delivery service, followed by television advertisements (17%) and word-of-mouth recommendations (20%).
7. **Factors Influencing Decision:** The top factors influencing the decision to use Zomato's food delivery service were variety of food options (61%), convenient delivery options (48%), and positive reviews and ratings (35%).
8. **Overall Satisfaction:** The majority of participants expressed satisfaction with Zomato's food delivery service, with 42% being very satisfied and 40% being satisfied. Only a small proportion (8%) reported being dissatisfied.
9. **Likelihood to Recommend:** A significant number of participants (80%) expressed a positive likelihood of recommending Zomato's food delivery service, with 36% being very likely and 44% being likely.
10. **Menu Options:** Overall, participants showed a positive perception of the menu options provided by Zomato's food delivery service, with 70% agreeing or strongly agreeing that the options were diverse and catered to different preferences.
11. **Pricing:** Participants generally perceived the prices of food items on Zomato's platform to be reasonable, with 69% agreeing or strongly agreeing.
12. **Delivery Process:** The delivery process was positively evaluated, with 78% of participants agreeing or strongly agreeing that it was efficient and timely.
13. **Promotional Offers:** The majority of participants (71%) found the promotional offers and discounts provided by Zomato's food delivery service to be appealing.

14. **Customer Support:** A large majority of participants (78%) agreed or strongly agreed that the customer support provided by Zomato's food delivery service was responsive and helpful.
 15. **Food Quality and Taste:** Most participants (72%) agreed or strongly agreed that Zomato's food delivery service met their expectations in terms of food quality and taste.
 16. **User Interface:** A significant number of participants (76%) found Zomato's app or website user-friendly and easy to navigate.
 17. **Range of Restaurants and Cuisines:** Overall, participants had a positive perception of the range of restaurants and cuisines available on Zomato's food delivery service, with 71% agreeing or strongly agreeing.
 18. **Communication and Updates:** The majority of participants (73%) agreed or strongly agreed that the communication and updates provided by Zomato's food delivery service regarding order status were clear and informative.
 19. **Overall Satisfaction:** Overall, a large majority of participants (78%) expressed satisfaction with their experience using Zomato's food delivery service.
 20. **Improvement Areas:** While the majority of participants were satisfied, a small proportion (9%) expressed some level of dissatisfaction or neutrality, indicating areas for improvement in certain
3. **Streamline Delivery Process:** The efficient and timely delivery process received positive feedback, but efforts should be made to maintain consistency and improve further. Ensuring proper training and coordination with delivery partners can help minimize delays and enhance the overall customer experience.
 4. **Promotional Offers and Discounts:** Participants found the promotional offers and discounts provided by Zomato appealing. Zomato should continue to introduce attractive offers, personalized deals, and loyalty programs to incentivize repeat orders and foster customer loyalty.
 5. **Proactive and Responsive Customer Support:** The positive feedback regarding customer support indicates that Zomato is on the right track. However, continuously investing in training and resources to maintain a responsive and helpful customer support team is crucial. Timely resolution of customer queries and concerns can significantly enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty.
 6. **Ensure Consistent Food Quality and Taste:** While the majority of participants were satisfied with the food quality and taste, maintaining consistency is essential. Zomato should establish quality control measures and regularly monitor partner restaurants to ensure that the delivered food consistently meets customer expectations.
 7. **User-Friendly Interface:** The positive perception of Zomato's app and website indicates a user-friendly interface. However, gathering user feedback and conducting usability testing can help identify areas for improvement and optimize the interface to further enhance the overall user experience.

SUGGESTIONS TO THE ORGANIZATION

Based on the findings of the study on Zomato's food delivery service and customer engagement, the following suggestions can be made:

1. **Enhance Variety of Food Options:** As the variety of food options was identified as a key factor influencing customer decision-making, Zomato should continue expanding its range of restaurants and cuisines to cater to diverse customer preferences. Regularly updating and introducing new options can help retain existing customers and attract new ones.
2. **Competitive Pricing Strategies:** While participants generally found Zomato's prices reasonable, it is important to continuously monitor and compare pricing with other platforms to ensure competitiveness. Offering occasional exclusive deals and discounts can further incentivize customers to choose Zomato over competitors.
8. **Effective Communication and Updates:** Zomato should continue providing clear and informative communication regarding order status to keep customers informed. Leveraging technologies such as real-time tracking and proactive notifications can help manage customer expectations and provide a seamless delivery experience.

By implementing these suggestions, Zomato can further enhance its marketing mix and customer engagement, leading to increased customer satisfaction, loyalty, and a competitive edge in the food delivery service industry.

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